

Appendix A: Observation Protocol

Topic	Questions (Observation focus)
Time	When does the meeting start? When does the meeting end?
Meeting environment	Physical/ online/ hybrid
Participants	What are the roles and other details of the participants? <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Number of attendees & their roles- Who leads/ facilitates the meeting?- Major tasks conducted by the participants
Activities	What are the various discussions and activities carried out in the meeting? <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Activities discussed related to RE- Challenges discussed related to RE activities.- How do they carry out Re-related activities?
Team members' personality-related observations	How do team members engage/ cooperate with others? Are there any conflicts within the team? How do the team handle these conflicts (if any)? How do they carry out discussions? The nature of the team members Are they interactive/ outgoing/ reserved? Impact on how they carry out work on RE-related activities and overall tasks?
Events	Are there any particular events or anything unanticipated?
Feelings	How is the atmosphere of the meeting?
Closing	How does the meeting end? Is there any post-meeting planned? How does the PM/ lead deal with the conflicts (if any)? Are there any offline chats/ meetings planned?